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**Application of genetic engineering in vertical farming to solve farmer's
plight and make India the food bowl of the world: A Review**

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Agriculture contributes 20.19% GDP to the Indian economy since it is practiced as the sole means of living for almost 60% of the employed population in India. The exponentially growing population accompanied by substantial growth in food demand has brought in serious concerns necessitating the maximization of food production per unit area of cultivation. The impending need to feed billions of humans and animals globally is fuelling innovation in the agricultural and food sectors. All sustainability factors including environmental, social, and economic advancements require consideration to produce sustainable urban food. A promising approach to address this issue is vertical farming, which is an energy-intensive system of agriculture involving a collaboration of multiple technologies for growing crops without agronomic constraints. However, usage of traditional or old seeds is a major drawback of this modern technology. The concept of vertical farming should not be confined to the aim of utilizing every inch of land, instead should be expanded, and thought about by entrepreneurs. For getting the most out of innovative methods of urban agriculture, plant genetic engineering tools should be incorporated and implemented as well. Genetically modified (GM) crops have been commercially used for more than a few decades with increased crop yield, reduced costs, enhanced nutrient composition, and improved food quality. Nevertheless, the advantages of future applications could be even bigger. The application of biotechnology in introducing GM crops in vertical farming could revolutionize the agro-sector to the next level. This review aims at stitching the gap between vertical farming and plant architecture by integrating genetic modifications with environmental modifications for the production of crops with assured quality and quantity independent of weather change, climatic constraints, and soil conditions. This innovation can not only help us meet the challenge in feeding India itself but also help our nation to become one of the world's leaders in agriculture.

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